

ELECTROCHEMICAL PLATING OF COMPOSITE COATINGS

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SUMMARY: The surface properties of structural units extremely influence their behaviour. In many cases the structural units are stressed in the surface region by a combination of mechanical, tribological, corrosive and thermal influences. Under these circumstances, deposition with composite coatings is an effective surface protection. These deposits can be coated on steel, light metals, ceramics, plastics and other materials. The composite coatings consist of a metal matrix with, in general, non-metal solid particles or short fibres. One of the most important coating process is the electrochemical plating. Following a survey on the manufacture, some properties, applications of composite coatings and new developments are presented. Especially fine particles of diameters less than 100 nm are available and are investigated in connection with electroplating experiments.

KEYWORDS: electrochemical plating, electrochemical composite deposition, nickel electrolytic, matrix materials, dispersal materials, solid particles, nano-particles, structure of coatings, microhardness of coatings, wear behaviour of coatings, nickel composite coatings

INTRODUCTION

Survey of Composite Coatings

The composition, structure and surface determine the properties of materials. The stress of materials causes a degradation of properties or even damages. The coating of materials can reduce these effects of stress in many cases. Especially the composite coatings are suitable. A great variety of coatings and as well as additional treatment processes are known (Fig. 1). Dispersal of solid phases combination of matrix (base material) and dispersal phases, determine the properties - therefore careful selection is very important. Mainly non-metal components in the form of particles or - in small amounts - of short fibres, are used. These second phases are incorporated during growth of the coating (e. g. electroplating from suspensions, thermal spraying) or later created inside the coatings (e. g. thermal treatment of electroless nickel coatings with phosphorus or boron causes precipitation hardening). Dispersed phases can also be incorporated into cavities within the coatings (e. g. infiltration of MoS₂ or polymers, production of phosphates or nitrides, incorporation of dispersed phases in pores or microcracks of chromium deposits [2]). Molten metal (e. g. steel) in a process called compound casting can contain dispersed carbides (e. g. VC, WC, MoC) [3] and will

Possibilities of Manufacture			
Electrochemical Plating		Thermal Spraying	
Electroless Plating	Electrophoresis	Plasma Welding	Deposit Welding
Melting		Melting on	
Multilayer	Nanolayer-sequences	Gradient Coatings	
Combination of different processes			
Additional Treatment			
Heat Treatment	Thermochemical Treatment	Laser-, Electron-, Plasma-Beam-Treatment	
Infiltration		Incorporation	

Fig. 1: Possibilities of manufacture and additional treatment of composite coatings

Fig. 2: Schematic depiction of a composite coating

be cast on the surface of highly stressed tools (e. g. drop forging die). By similar methods, laser or electron beams (remelting), plasma (plasma welding) or deposit welding can be used. In this way hard alloys on basis iron, nickel or cobalt with carbides, borides and others have been produced. Multilayer and nano-coatings are also kinds of composite coatings. Such systems are useful as deposits on tools (particularly CVD). Similar layers are produced with PVD. Gradient coatings can be produced e. g. by thermal spraying. Also combinations among diverse coating processes are possible, e. g. a combination of electrochemical with PVD or thermochemical processes. From the large number of methods incorporating solid particles into coatings, most already frequently contain the dispersal phase within the coating materials or coating medium.

Electrochemical plating of composite coatings and the thermal spraying of composite coatings presently are one of the most important techniques for fabrication of composite coatings. Some examples are the electroplating of Ni-, Fe - and Al - dispersion coatings. Important applications are found in motor production (especially small motors for tools, such as power saws but also for motor cycles and cars) and to prevent or reduce wear of tools. Ni- and CBN- dispersal coatings are used for abrasive tools. Electrochemical composite deposits find applications in textile industry (e. g. to rough up fibres) and for improvement of unclosed pair elements. The thermal sprayed composite coatings will be applied at high tribological and corrosive loads, e. g. for energy generation (e. g. gas turbines), steel manufacture and metal forming. [4] - [6]

Structure - Properties - Relations of Electrochemical Composite Coatings

The composite coatings depending on application consist of a matrix and various dispersal phases (see Fig. 2). Material and structural interactions of different constituent phases induce modified composite properties. The dispersal phases can change the coatings structure and the coatings properties as well as the surface properties and the materials bond.

Composite coatings are used for the primary coating and for repair coating. They induce

- raising of strength and support effect (high strong phases in an unhardened, tough matrix)
- formation of zones sensitive to absorb or scatter energy, relax stress and divert, catch or bridge cracks
- improvement of tribological properties (wear reduction, friction modification)
- improvement of corrosion resistance and of decorative effect
- improvement of thermal resistance
- raising of porosity and roughness
- raising of catalysing effects
- production of barrier effects (e. g. thermal insulation).

Examples for matrix and dispersal materials are:

matrix materials

- metals (e. g. Ni; Cu; Fe; Cr; Co; Ag; Au; Zn; Sn; Cd; Pb; Pd; Al)
- metal alloys (e. g. NiCr; NiAg; CuNi; CuAg; NiCrBSi; steel alloys)

dispersal materials

- carbides (e. g. SiC; TiC; Cr₃C₂; WC; B₄C; ZrC; HfC)
- oxides (e. g. Al₂O₃; SiO₂; TiO₂; Cr₂O₃; ZrO₂; UO₂; BeO)
- borides, nitrides (e.g. Cr₃B₂; TiB₂; ZrB₂; HfB₂; BN; B₄N; TiN; AlN)
- diamond
- graphite; MoS₂
- others (e.g. glass; CaF₂; BaSO₄)

The incorporated particles modify coating properties in various ways (Fig. 3):

- they influence the material structure of coating during the coating growth
- modification of coating properties by their pure existence of the particles in the coating.

Fig. 3: Influence of hard particles on structure and properties (G shear modulus, b BURGERS vector, N particle number, V particle volumen, τ shear stress, τ_{OR} OROWAN stress)

The existence of particles in the electrolyte, especially in the region of phase boundary, influence the electrochemical system and therefore the material structure of coatings materials. The electrical-insulating particles partly blocking the specimen surface, whereby the cathode-side current density and the cathode-polarization increases. This leads finally to a reduction of the matrix-crystallite. The mechanically properties can be improved. Fig. 3 points out, that incoherent build in particles effect a dispersion hardening (orowan-mechanism).

In particular the strengths raising is based on the interactions between the particles and the dislocations. A cutting of the particles by the dislocation lines is dominant in case of coherent particles. If the coherence decreases, the particles are surrounded with a coherence field which hinders the motion of dislocations. Biggest work hardening effect will occur if the particles are incorporated incoherently and are harder than the matrix. Then the particles cannot be cut and must be encircled by forming dislocation rings. The Orowan-mechanism is valid in the range of micro elongation; the obstacles are encircled at higher elongation's by cross slide [7].

It can be seen from the theory of dispersion hardening that realising maximum hardness small and hard particles of uniform shape have to be finely dispersed in the coating. The most favourable particle size (the critical diameter) should be between 10 and 20 nm. Optimal work hardening will be realised if on the one hand the particle diameter is near the critical diameter for

a high strength and on the other hand somewhat over the critical diameter for a sufficient toughness. The interaction components between particles and dislocations will decrease and therefore the dispersion hardening effect as well, if the diameter of particles is higher than the critical diameter. For thermodynamically stable particles their spatial distribution will be preserved at higher temperatures as well. In this case the particles prevent recrystallization and grain growth and raise the high temperature strength. The existence of particles in the coating results in matrix work hardening, reduces the internal tensile stresses and improves the tribological surface properties (e. g. decrease of adhesion and friction).

Properties of metal matrix and of particles frequently complement each other synergetically. The content, distribution, shape, size and the hardness of hard particles and properties of matrix cause the strength and wear behaviour of coatings.

The application of the very fine nano-particles yields two particular advantages:
a genuine dispersion-hardening effect,
the reduction of the layer - thickness.

Until recently sufficiently fine particles, necessary for the dispersion hardening, so far have not been available. But since a few years some companies and institutes are offering powders with diameters of less than 100 nm. Our institute was one of the first to carry out experimental investigations for applications of nano-particles.

EXPERIMENTAL

It is well-known that the technological realisation is based on two basic principles:

- Small particles can be dispersed in the electrolyte. They get to the phase boundary between electrolyte and cathode-surface as a result of external, forced convection and - probably - of small electrophoresis effects. As a consequence of migration and of electrostatic effects the particles move to the region of deposit and are inserted. Where they have to be fixed until they are buried by the electro-crystallising matrix.
- Bigger particles are forced to sink to the cathode surface by suitable technical methods or they are already in a "fixed bed" and then incorporated into the growing layer.

The choice of fabrication method depends on particle size. The dispersal method can be applied up to particle diameters of approximately 10 μm . Examples of coatings with fine, but also with coarse particles are shown in Fig. 4 and 5.

Fig. 4: Micrograph showing a Ni-SiC-composite coating for grinding

Fig. 5: Micrograph showing a conventional Ni-SiC-composite coating

Our investigations are carried out applying a special electrolyte bath based on nickel sulphate with SiO₂- nano-particles of fixed diameters of both 100 or 500 nm (Monospher ®, Fa. Merck, Darmstadt, Germany). Later on investigations will be carried out with smaller particles (up to ca. 10 nm diameter). The particles were dispersed in the electrolyte-fluid by mechanical stirring. At the samples surface particles were placed in the increasing nickel deposition by electro-crystallization (see Fig. 6).

Fig. 6: SEM micrographs of surface electroplated Ni-SiO₂ - coatings

To render the placement of the small particles, different problems have to be solved:

The dispersion of the particles in the electrolyte fluid. That means that the particles are wettable and do not reaggregate in the electrolyte bath.

The creation of a stable suspension fluid.

A homogenous distribution of the installed particles in the cathodic deposition.

The particles have to possess a sufficient hardness.

Regarding to electroplating, several problems must be solved in future. The field of research "nano-particles" for the manufacture of dispersal coatings is still developing. For instance, investigations are necessary for the creation of stable suspension or for the moving of nano-particles to the cathode. The agglomeration of powder-particles in the electrolytic bath must be prevented. Also particle properties as e. g. hardness need improvement.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

It was achieved to install nano-particles in a electrolytic deposited nickel-layer (see Fig. 6, 7). The incorporation of solid particles in the coating was evaluated just qualitatively by image analysis. But it was obviously clear that the solid content of the coating increases with the content in the electrolytic bath.

Fig. 7: Micrograph showing a Ni-SiO₂ (Monospher ®) - composite coating

A comparison with Al₂O₃- and SiC-particles of diameters 5 to 10 µm was performed by separate experiments. These results were published in former papers and are verified by other authors.

It is approved to increase the hardness within the incorporation of solid particles into the layer (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8: Microhardness of nickel composite coatings as function of the particle size and content in the electrolytic bath

The increase of the wear resistance of these layers was pointed out by the oscillation-wear test (see Fig. 9).

The test under oscillation load creates a wear trace, a calotte in the specimen. The specimen moves oscillation under the counter-body. The counter-body is a ball (ceramic or steel) and has a diameter of 5 mm [8]. Parameter of the test are: Load $F_N = 10\text{ N}$, the frequency $f = 20\text{ Hz}$, testing time $t = 20\text{ min}$. The oscillation wear is determined $J_h^* = d_s^2 (8R)^{-1} (R - \text{counter-body radius, } d_s \text{ calotte width})$.

Fig. 9: Oscillation wear behaviour of nickel composite coatings (hard particles content in the electrolytic bath)

The results of oscillation wear are interesting because coatings containing monospheres are better because they show less wear than those with alumina. It is most likely that the reason is particle form. Monospheres are of spherical shape whereas alumina particles have a sharp-edged form and therefore promote the abrasive wear. It was shown that the placement of nano-particles also effects an improvement of the deposition. It can be proved that the spherical nano-particles are capable to open new and favourable options for electrochemical plating of dispersal coatings.

CONCLUSIONS

It can be established, that

- * it is possible to install extreme high grade particles (nano particles with diameters from 1 μm to 10 nm) into electrolytic deposited layers.
- * within the deposition of the high grade particles the hardness and the wear-resistance was improved.
- * with these nano particles it is possible to produce dispersion hardening layers.

It can be proved that the spherical nano-particles are capable of opening new and favourable options for electrochemical plating of dispersal coatings.

It can be stated that composite coatings, especially the electrochemical deposition offer favourable options for the improvement of the tribological properties of materials and thus make broad applications in significant scale possible.

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